

Vertical Seismic Protection of Structures with Inerter-Based Negative Stiffness Absorbers

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Abstract

One of the most effective approaches for seismic protection of structural systems is isolation. The majority of existing seismic protection systems are related to horizontal ground motion and only few focus on vertical seismic components, as this would require vertical flexibility, a feature conflicting with the need for sufficient support of the isolated structure. In order to overcome this difficulty, a novel vertical Stiff Dynamic Absorber (SDA) is proposed that combines a Quasi-Zero Stiffness design including negative stiffness elements, an enhanced Tuned Mass Damper, and Inerter elements. The present work deals with the optimization problem for the determination of the various design parameters of the proposed configuration, aiming at minimizing the vertical accelerations induced on the structure while keeping the displacement within reasonable limits. The values of the optimized design parameters depend only on the characteristics of the isolated structure irrespectively of the excitation input. This feature differentiates the proposed SDA from similar versions found in the literature and renders the design applicable for use across a wide range of vertical vibration control applications. The proposed configuration is designed to achieve great acceleration isolation without compromising the weight-bearing capacity of the structure. This is realized through the appropriate determination of the static and dynamic stiffnesses via a novel calculation approach that is based on the initial static equilibrium point. The role of various design factors is investigated based on time-history responses of a reference structure to artificial accelerograms matching EC8 criteria, and the effect of the optimized SDA is evaluated on real earthquake records, confirming its capacity to greatly reduce the response to structure accelerations. The selection of the design parameters is based on engineering criteria and an indicative implementation of the design elements is included, demonstrating the feasibility of the proposed configuration.

Keywords Vertical Seismic Protection; Negative Stiffness; KDamper; Damping; Vibration Absorption;

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1 Introduction

Earthquakes represent one of the major environmental hazards. During 2011, for example, over 20,000 people died and about one million people lost their homes globally due to earthquakes and their consequences. Less hazardous but also impactful phenomena include the effects of a wide class of ground vibrations generated by heavy and high-speed vehicles such as trains and trucks, construction activities (e.g. dynamic compaction, roadbed compaction, pile driving) or blasts with a frequency spectrum in the order of a few Hz. The conventional design approach to address such issues consists of stiff and highly damped structures. Apart from the technical and financial constraints regarding their realization (e.g. current unavailability of large sized dampers, cases of heavy and costly structures etc.) such designs may result to adverse effects concerning aspects of their desired dynamic behavior. For example, stiff and highly damped structures can enhance the transfer of base acceleration excitations to the main structure. This may result to damaging effects in the interior of the structure relating, e.g. to the secondary loads (machines, sensitive equipment etc.) in the case of earthquakes.

Isolation appears to be a promising alternative [1], as it is based on the concept of altering the dynamics of the system and reducing ground-induced vibrations, rather than on increasing the resistance capacity of the structure. The concept of isolation relies on a flexible layer between the structure and its base. This way, the fundamental natural frequency of the base isolated system is significantly smaller, and thus the structure can absorb less energy from the broad base excitation frequency spectrum. However, in order to isolate the building from its base, large displacements may occur due to the fundamental dynamic behavior of the system, which can be even in the range of tens of centimeters for certain excitations. These displacements can hardly be acceptable for numerous reasons such as structural pounding, sensitivity in horizontal loads, proper connection for utilities and more, thus rendering this concept inadequate for retrofitting especially in the vertical direction.

The above findings have motivated the development of alternative vibration control strategies which, among others, include: (i) Tuned Mass Dampers (TMDs), (ii) Inerters, (iii) Negative Stiffness Devices (NSD) and Quasi Zero Stiffness (QZS) oscillators, and (iv) Negative Stiffness driven Absorbers/KDampers.

The Tuned Mass Damper (TMD) has a long history with applications in several types of engineering structures, such as high-rise buildings and skyscrapers [2]–[4], bridges [5], wind and wave excitation in wind turbines [6] etc. In addition, the TMD can be used as a possible supplement to the conventional base isolation approaches, implemented within the bases of structures, aiming to reduce the displacement demand [7]–[9]. The main disadvantages of vibration absorption techniques that use a TMD-related approach are associated with the requirement for large additional masses in order for the TMD to be effective and with the fact that a slight alteration of its parameters can alter the TMD tuning and consequently significantly reduce the system's performance [10].

In an attempt to reduce the requirements for heavy oscillating masses under the TMD concept the inerter was introduced in the early 2000s [11], [12]. The inerter is a two-terminal element which has the property of generating a force at its ends that is proportional to the relative acceleration of its terminals. The main advantage of the inerter lies in the fact that it does not need to have large masses in order to achieve the same inertia effect as the additional mass required under the TMD approach. Some notable designs for seismic isolation of building structures can be found in [13]–[19]. The essential limitation of the inerter is the complex and elaborate mechanical design configurations needed for its implementation and the reduction of the effective damping of the system due to the increase of the effective mass. Moreover, the major disadvantage of the inerter in seismic isolation applications is that it enhances the transfer of base acceleration excitations to the main structure significantly more than the highly damped base isolation system [20]. As mentioned, this can result to damaging effects in the interior of the structure.

A parallel direction to the various TMD approaches is the concept of introducing negative stiffness (NS) elements for vibration absorption. The use of negative stiffness elements (or “anti-springs”) for vibration isolation was first introduced in the pioneering works of Molyneaux [21] and of Platus [22]. The central concept of these approaches is the significant reduction of the isolator's stiffness, which consequently leads to the decrease of the natural frequency of the system to very low levels. This type of oscillator can find application in seismic isolation [23]–[28], as while the fundamental frequency decreases, the structure attracts smaller seismic forces. Under this scope, the so called “Quasi-Zero Stiffness” (QZS) oscillators have been proposed [26]. An initial comprehensive review of such designs can be found in [29]. Nagarajaiah et. al [30] introduced a new structural modification approach for the seismic protection of structures using an adaptive negative stiffness device that resulted in the decrease of the dynamic forces imposed on the structure. The QZS oscillators are essentially designs of a non-linear stiffness, combining a positive spring in parallel with a non-linear one, thus exhibiting a negative stiffness region under nominal load. This way the QZS oscillators combine a high static stiffness, capable of maintaining the structural load, with a low dynamic

stiffness, enabling a low isolation frequency. However, QZS oscillators offer a low damping capacity. In addition, even small load disturbances around the static equilibrium point of the QZS designs can significantly affect their response.

Extending the concept of the traditional Tuned Mass Dampers, the KDamper [31], a novel passive vibration absorption and damping concept has been introduced. Compared to the TMD, the KDamper uses an additional negative stiffness spring that connects the additional mass to the ground. This NS spring generates a force in phase with the acceleration response acting essentially as an inertial force on the additional mass. In this way, the performance of the KDamper can be drastically increased, just by increasing the value of the negative stiffness spring and without the need to increase the value of the additional mass. Thus the KDamper exhibits extraordinary damping and absorption properties, with relatively small (even minimal) values of the additional mass. Although the KDamper incorporates a NS element, it is designed to be both statically and dynamically stable. Thus the system can be designed with the same overall static stiffness as a traditional reference original oscillator, while simultaneously offering significantly enhanced damping properties. Since the presence of a NS spring in series with a positive stiffness spring can result to a NS value, the static behavior of the KDamper can be controlled to be similar to that of a QZS oscillator, ensuring both high static and low dynamic stiffnesses.

A number of KDamper designs [31], [32] and extensions [33]–[37] have been applied as seismic absorbers in the bases of structures. Their overall static stiffness is allowed to vary from low values that are similar to that of seismic isolation systems, to values corresponding to significantly higher stiffnesses. In the case of low stiffness, the KDamper demonstrates a behavior similar to that of a base isolated system, however combining this feature with drastically increased damping. In the opposite case, the KDamper has shown the ability to drastically reduce the structure base displacements relative to the ground to the range of few centimeters, while maintaining the absolute structure accelerations within reasonable limits. This aforementioned result implies that the KDamper can be used as an alternative method to conventional base isolation systems, enabling its implementation (under certain conditions) even for retrofitting existing structures.

Quite recently the extended KDamper has been used in parallel to an inerter [38] for vertical seismic protection. Under a proper optimization procedure this combination resulted to a configuration with a relatively high vertical static and dynamic stiffness, ensuring acceptable levels of vertical static displacement while achieving a satisfactory reduction of the vertical accelerations induced to the structure. This concept is the underlying notion and configuration of the Stiff Dynamic Absorbers (SDA).

The SDA, proposed in this paper, has several novel aspects that greatly enhance its efficiency and feasibility as a method for vertical seismic protection. The first key difference between the design proposed herein and the one proposed in [38] is that, depending on the initial static equilibrium position of the configuration, this system can be designed with a sufficiently high static stiffness ensuring acceptable static deflections, and with a low dynamic stiffness leading to a notably improved dynamic behavior. The second important difference lies in the introduction of a design method that is based on a new more general objective function for optimization; this objective function depends solely on the characteristics of the system rather than on a specific excitation spectrum. Finally, the possibility of introducing various inerter elements in the SDA configuration is examined with the aim to reduce the internal displacements of the SDA mechanism and thus provide a more realistic design for the positive and negative stiffness elements, as well as the linear dampers.

The system is configured for a reference structure under a proper optimization procedure and a detailed evaluation of alternative designs is conducted using artificial accelerograms. The efficiency of the optimized design is subsequently tested on real earthquakes. Results indicate that the proposed SDA achieves a great reduction in peak structure acceleration vs. the conventional damping system, while maintaining the structure relative displacement at reasonable levels and without compromising the weight-bearing capacity of the initial structure. The analysis of real earthquake cases is introduced as a tool to evaluate the SDA comparative advantages, confirming that the proposed design is especially efficient in dramatically reducing structure accelerations in the low-frequency range of ~ 2 -5Hz, where the conventional damping system would be insufficient, and in many cases even counter-effective. Moreover, it is proven in this work that the system can be accurately optimized via an objective function based only on the system's characteristics and not a specific excitation input, which means that a unique optimal SDA design can be used for protection of the structure against any type of excitation within the frequency range of interest. Furthermore, the dynamics of the problem suggest that the same design approach can be extended to a wide range of vertical dynamic absorption applications including low-frequency machine mounts and impact noise insulation, with a simple adjustment of the design parameters.

2 Theoretical Background

2.1 Conventional Single-degree of freedom damping system and transfer functions

The fundamental principle of seismic isolation is to decrease the natural frequency of the system below the dominant energy-containing frequencies of ground motions, and thus significantly reduce the peak accelerations of the structure. A major constraint when following this approach lies in the weakened static loading capacity of the structure due to its decreased overall stiffness causing large static displacements. The vertical static deflection, denoted by X_{VSD} , of the single-degree of freedom (SDoF) system presented in Fig 1.a is calculated:

$$X_{VSD} = \frac{mg}{k} = \frac{g}{(2\pi f)^2} \quad (1)$$

Fig 1 (a) Conventional vibration damper; (b) KDamper concept; (c) Proposed Stiff Dynamic Absorber (SDA); (d) Stiff Dynamic Absorber with internal inerters (SDA-II)

The equation of motion of the system is

$$m\ddot{u}_s + c\dot{u}_s + ku_s = -m\ddot{X}_G \quad (2)$$

where $u_s = X_s - X_G$. Assuming a harmonic base excitation in the form of $\ddot{X}_G(t) = A_G e^{i\omega t}$, the steady-state response is

$$u_s(t) = \tilde{U}_s e^{i\omega t} \quad (3.a)$$

where \tilde{U}_s denotes the complex amplitude. In terms of absolute structure acceleration, the steady-state response is

$$\ddot{X}_S(t) = A_S e^{i\omega t} \quad (3.b)$$

where A_S denotes the complex amplitude.

The equation of motion of the SDof system is written in the following form:

$$-\omega^2 m \tilde{U}_s + j\omega c \tilde{U}_s + k \tilde{U}_s = -m A_G \quad (4)$$

The Transfer Functions of the system are calculated equal to

$$\tilde{H}_{US} = \tilde{U}_s / A_G = -\tilde{H}^{-1} m \quad (5)$$

$$\tilde{H}_{AS} = A_S / A_G = -\omega^2 \tilde{X}_S / A_G = 1 - \omega^2 \tilde{H}_{US} \quad (6)$$

where

$$\tilde{H} = [-\omega^2 m + j\omega c + k] \quad (7)$$

The natural frequency and the damping ratio of the SDoF isolated system are

$$f = \frac{1}{2\pi} \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} \quad (8)$$

$$\zeta = \frac{c}{2\sqrt{mk}} \quad (9)$$

2.2 Stiff Dynamic Absorber elastic forces and static equilibrium position

The proposed SDA is designed to combine a high static stiffness in order to support the weight of the structure and allow acceptable static vertical displacements, together with a low dynamic stiffness in order to achieve sufficient vertical vibration isolation. The latter feature is facilitated by the introduction of the negative stiffness element in the internal configuration. Fig 2 shows the schematic configuration of the SDA spring assembly, including an indicative implementation of the negative stiffness (NS) spring. The detailed analysis of this NS spring is performed in Appendix A. In the static equilibrium position Fig 2(a) the following equations hold

$$k_R(l_{RS} - l_{RI}) + k_P(l_{PS} - l_{PI}) = -mg \quad (10.a)$$

$$-k_P(l_{PS} - l_{PI}) + N(u_S) = -m_D g \quad (10.b)$$

where $N(u)$ is the force of the negative stiffness spring configuration, l_{RI}, l_{PI} are the initial lengths of the springs k_R, k_P and l_{RS}, l_{PS} are the corresponding spring lengths in the static equilibrium position. In view of eq. (10) the deformations V_R, V_P of the springs k_R, k_P are:

$$V_{RS} = l_{RI} - l_{RS} = [(m + m_D)g + N(u_S)]/k_R \quad (11.a)$$

$$V_{PS} = l_{PI} - l_{PS} = [m_D g + N(u_S)]/k_P \quad (11.b)$$

Fig 2 Schematic configuration of the SDA spring assembly, including an indicative implementation of the NS element using a pair of compressed springs and a pair of mechanical linkages. (a) Static equilibrium position, and (b) perturbations around the static equilibrium position under an external force f

When an external force f acts as a perturbation from the static position, the following equations hold for the elastic and the external forces:

$$k_R(l_R - l_{Rl}) + k_P(l_P - l_{Pl}) = -mg + f \quad (12.a)$$

$$-k_P(l_P - l_{Pl}) + N(u) = -m_D g \quad (12.b)$$

Combining equations (10), (11) and (12) the following equations are obtained

$$k_R x + k_P(x - y) = f \quad (13.a)$$

$$-k_P(x - y) + N_D(y) = 0, \quad (13.b)$$

where l_R, l_P are the lengths of the springs k_R, k_P and

$$l_R = l_{RS} + x \quad (14.a)$$

$$l_P = l_{PS} + x - y \quad (14.b)$$

$$u = u_S + y \quad (14.c)$$

$$N_D(u) = N(u) - N(u_S) = N(u) - N_S \quad (14.d)$$

Equation (13.b) leads to the expression

$$x = y + N_D(y)/k_P, \quad (15)$$

which can be solved to yield y as a function of x . As a result, the force f can be obtained as a function of the variable x only:

$$f = k_R x + N_D(y(x)) \quad (16)$$

Equation (16) presents the force $f(x)$ as a function of the perturbation x of the mass m from the equilibrium position. The derivative of $f(x)$ with respect to the variable x presents the total k_T stiffness of the combined system:

$$k_T(x) = \frac{\partial f(x)}{\partial x} \quad (17)$$

In view of equations (15) and (16) and through further elaboration of equation (17) we obtain

$$k_T(x) = k_R + \frac{k_P k_N(y(x))}{k_P + k_N(y(x))} \quad (18)$$

where

$$k_N(x) = \frac{\partial N(y)}{\partial y} = \frac{\partial N(u)}{\partial u} \quad (19)$$

Assuming that $N(u)$ varies linearly around the static equilibrium point u_S in the range of perturbations x and y , k_N can be considered constant

$$k_N(y) = k_N = \text{constant} \quad (20)$$

The quantity

$$k_T = k_R + \frac{k_P k_N}{k_P + k_N} \quad (21)$$

is also constant and equal to the total stiffness resulting from the spring elements k_R , k_P , k_N . Equations (10) and (11) indicate that an infinite number of initial static equilibrium positions of the SDA can in principle occur, depending on the initial position u_S of the negative stiffness spring assembly. In this paper, the following initial configuration shall be used:

$$u_S = 0 \quad (22)$$

This configuration combines two advantages. First, the negative stiffness force is symmetric around the position $u = u_S = 0$. Second, and most important, is the fact that in this position $N(u_S) = 0$. As a result, equations (11) take the form:

$$V_{RS} = (m + m_D)g/k_R \quad (23.a)$$

$$V_{PS} = m_D g/k_P \quad (23.b)$$

Equation (23) indicates that in the initial static equilibrium position, the entire structure weight can be supported only by the spring k_R . As a result, and since $m_D \ll m$ for typical SDA designs, the vertical static deflection of the structure under its weight is:

$$X_{VSD} = mg/k_R \quad (24)$$

Since k_N is negative and if k_P is chosen so that:

$$k_P > |k_N| \quad (25)$$

equation (21) implies that:

$$k_T < k_R \quad (26)$$

Therefore, similarly to the QSZ oscillators, the SDA can be designed with a high static stiffness $k_S = k_R$ and a low dynamic stiffness $k_D = k_T$.

2.3 Stiff Dynamic Absorber dynamic response and transfer functions

Following the above observations and assuming a suitable range of perturbations from equilibrium, the spring elements k_R , k_P , k_N of the SDA mechanical analogue (Fig 1(c)) can be considered constant for the purpose of the dynamic analysis of the system. Denoting the relative displacement between the structure and ground as $u_S = X_S - X_G$ the equations of motion for the two masses are:

$$(m_S + b_R)\ddot{u}_S + c_P(\dot{u}_S - \dot{u}_D) + k_R u_S + k_P(u_S - u_D) = -m_S \ddot{X}_G \quad (27.a)$$

$$m_D \ddot{u}_D + c_P(\dot{u}_D - \dot{u}_S) + c_N \dot{u}_D + k_N u_D + k_P(u_D - u_S) = -m_D \ddot{X}_G \quad (27.b)$$

The steady state responses of the system are

$$u_S(t) = \tilde{U}_S e^{j\omega t} \quad (28.a)$$

$$u_D(t) = \tilde{U}_D e^{j\omega t} \quad (28.b)$$

where \tilde{U}_S, \tilde{U}_D , denote the response complex amplitudes.

In terms of absolute acceleration, the steady-state responses of the system are given by

$$\ddot{X}_S(t) = A_S e^{j\omega t} \quad (28.c)$$

$$\ddot{X}_D(t) = A_D e^{j\omega t} \quad (28.d)$$

where A_S, A_D denote the complex amplitudes of the structure and oscillating mass accelerations respectively.

The abovementioned equations of motion of the system hence become:

$$-\omega^2 (m_S + b_R) \tilde{U}_S + j\omega c_P (\tilde{U}_S - \tilde{U}_D) + k_R \tilde{U}_S + k_P (\tilde{U}_S - \tilde{U}_D) = -m_S A_G \quad (29.a)$$

$$-\omega^2 m_D \tilde{U}_D + j\omega c_P (\tilde{U}_D - \tilde{U}_S) + j\omega c_N \tilde{U}_D + k_N \tilde{U}_D + k_P (\tilde{U}_D - \tilde{U}_S) = -m_D A_G \quad (29.b)$$

The resulting transfer functions (TFs) can be derived (see also Appendix B):

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{H}_{US} \\ \tilde{H}_{UD} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{U}_S / A_G \\ \tilde{U}_D / A_G \end{bmatrix} = H^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} m_S \\ m_D \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

$$\tilde{H}_{AS} = A_S / A_G = 1 - \omega^2 \tilde{H}_{US} \quad (31.a)$$

$$\tilde{H}_{AD} = A_D / A_G = 1 - \omega^2 \tilde{H}_{UD} \quad (31.b)$$

where

$$\tilde{H} = \begin{bmatrix} -\omega^2 (m_S + b_R) + j\omega c_P + (k_R + k_P) & -(j\omega c_P + k_P) \\ -(j\omega c_P + k_P) & -\omega^2 m_D + j\omega (c_P + c_N) + (k_N + k_P) \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

The following quantities represent the area under the transfer functions of the system and are indicators of the transmissibility of the system within the frequency range of interest (ω_1 to ω_2). These quantities are independent of the external excitation and could be conveniently used as an objective function of an optimization problem of low frequency vertical vibration control, as discussed in detail in paragraph 3.4.

$$Q_{US} = \int_{\omega_1}^{\omega_2} |\tilde{H}_{US}(\omega)|^2 d\omega \quad (33.a)$$

$$Q_{UD} = \int_{\omega_1}^{\omega_2} |\tilde{H}_{UD}(\omega)|^2 d\omega \quad (33.b)$$

$$Q_{AS} = \int_{\omega_1}^{\omega_2} |\tilde{H}_{AS}(\omega)|^2 d\omega \quad (33.c)$$

In past literature the frequency content of the external excitation was taken into account for the design of the stiff dynamic absorber, as is the case of the extended version of KDamper implemented for vertical seismic protection [38]. In this context the response power spectral densities have been calculated

$$S_{US}(\omega) = |\tilde{H}_{US}(\omega)|^2 S_A(\omega) \quad (34.a)$$

$$S_{UD}(\omega) = |\tilde{H}_{UD}(\omega)|^2 S_A(\omega) \quad (34.b)$$

$$S_{AS}(\omega) = |\tilde{H}_{AS}(\omega)|^2 S_A(\omega) \quad (34.c)$$

where S_A the PSD of the ground motion acceleration. Equations (34) are valid subject to the conditions of stationarity and ergodicity of the applied excitations (see e.g. Chapter 14 of [39]). A discussion of this issue, together with a

detailed account of the calculation of S_A , is given in Appendix C. An indicator of the total energy content of the response has been defined in [38] as the root mean square (RMS) value of the response quantities:

$$R_{US} = \sqrt{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{US}(\omega) d\omega} \quad (35.a)$$

$$R_{UD} = \sqrt{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{UD}(\omega) d\omega} \quad (35.b)$$

$$R_{AS} = \sqrt{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{AS}(\omega) d\omega} \quad (35.c)$$

Next, the following quantities concerning the system configuration are introduced:

$$m_D = \mu_D m_S \quad (36.a)$$

$$b_R = \mu_R m_S \quad (36.b)$$

$$\zeta_N = \frac{c_N}{2\sqrt{m_S k_R}} \quad (37.a)$$

$$\zeta_P = \frac{c_P}{2\sqrt{m_S k_R}} \quad (37.b)$$

2.4 Alternative design - Stiff Dynamic Absorber equipped with internal inerters (SDA-II)

In addition to the reference SDA configuration shown in Fig 1(c), the efficiency of an alternative design (SDA-II) is explored as shown in Fig 1(d). Two internal inerters b_P, b_N are introduced and placed in parallel to the stiffness elements k_P, k_N . Under this design, the equations of motion (29) take the form:

$$-\omega^2(m_S + b_R)\tilde{U}_S - \omega^2 b_P(\tilde{U}_S - \tilde{U}_D) + j\omega c_P(\tilde{U}_S - \tilde{U}_D) + k_R \tilde{U}_S + k_P(\tilde{U}_S - \tilde{U}_D) = -m_S A_G \quad (38.a)$$

$$-\omega^2(m_D + b_N)\tilde{U}_D - \omega^2 b_P(\tilde{U}_D - \tilde{U}_S) + j\omega c_P(\tilde{U}_D - \tilde{U}_S) + j\omega c_N \tilde{U}_D + k_N \tilde{U}_D + k_P(\tilde{U}_D - \tilde{U}_S) = -m_D A_G \quad (38.b)$$

The transfer function matrix, equation (31) is now:

$$\tilde{H} = \begin{bmatrix} -\omega^2(m_S + b_R + b_P) + j\omega c_P + (k_R + k_P) & -(-\omega^2 b_P + j\omega c_P + k_P) \\ -(-\omega^2 b_P + j\omega c_P + k_P) & -\omega^2(m_D + b_N + b_P) + j\omega(c_P + c_N) + (k_N + k_P) \end{bmatrix} \quad (39)$$

The equivalent masses for each inerter are defined as:

$$b_P = \mu_P m_S \quad (40.a)$$

$$b_N = \mu_N m_S \quad (40.b)$$

The impact of the additional inerters is presented in paragraph 4.4.

3 Optimization of Stiff Dynamic Absorber parameters

3.1 Statement of optimization problem

The optimization problem addresses the determination of the SDA's design parameters so as to minimize the response structure acceleration to a given excitation input, while maintaining the structure's relative displacement

within reasonable limits, thus ensuring feasibility of the design. The structure response acceleration depends on the transmissibility of the system, and more specifically on the acceleration transfer function \tilde{H}_{AS} (eq. 31.a).

3.2 Fixed parameters

The following are considered fixed parameters of the system with regards to the optimization problem:

- i. X_{VSD} : The static deflection of the structure depends on the initial stiffness of the structure k_R and on its mass as stated in Equation (24). In the reference optimization problem, X_{VSD} is taken equal to 2cm, while paragraph 4.5 presents the optimization results when X_{VSD} takes different values in the range [1-3] (cm).
- ii. m_S, m_D : The reference structure mass m_S is taken 1000 kg. The small oscillating mass m_D is determined through (36.a) where μ_D is taken equal to 5%.
- iii. $\varepsilon_N, \varepsilon_P, \varepsilon_R$: Variations from the design values of the various stiffness can occur due to various factors, such as temperature variations, manufacturing tolerances, or nonlinear behavior. The values of $\varepsilon_N, \varepsilon_P, \varepsilon_R$ are taken equal to 10%, 5% and 5% respectively.
- iv. μ_N, μ_P : The equivalent masses of the additional inerters are set to zero for the initial SDA design; in the case of the alternative design explored in paragraph 4.4 (SDA-with Internal Inerters) these are considered fixed parameters with a value of 5%.

3.3 Dependent & independent design variables

Having assigned values to the fixed parameters based on previous KDamper-based designs [34], the four independent design variables that are optimized under the proposed method are:

- k_N : The NS element maximum value is equal to -100 N/m per kg of structure mass, and the minimum value is equal to -800 N/m per kg. These limits are selected based on mechanisms [33], [40] that generate NS with conventional stiffness elements (coil springs), similar to the one proposed in Section 2 of this paper.
- c_N, c_P : The damping coefficients implemented in parallel to the stiffness elements k_N and k_P have an upper limit regarding their damping ratios ζ_N, ζ_P equal to 1.0%. The resulting values of the damping coefficients are low, and thus common linear damping devices can be employed [41].
- μ_R : The inertance ratio of the inverter, b_R , placed between the base and the structure. The upper limit of μ_R is set to 1.0. The inverter can be realized through a leverage mechanism that increases the effective mass of the system in the vertical direction with a counterweight [42], which when properly designed can provide an inertance ratio up to 1, with small counterweight masses.

The positive stiffness element k_P is derived from the static stability limit case as a dependent variable. To ensure that potential loss of the static stability is prevented, the possible variations of k_P should be taken into consideration in the design and optimization of the system. The stiffness parameters of the system may present significant fluctuations since almost all negative stiffness designs result from unstable non-linear configurations [43]. Consequently, an increase of the absolute value of k_N and/or a decrease of the values of k_P and k_R by a factor $\varepsilon_N, \varepsilon_P$ respectively, may result in the system being unstable. In the limit case that the total overall stiffness k_T as calculated by equation (21) is equal to zero, the system is unstable:

$$k_T = 0 \Leftrightarrow (1 - \varepsilon_R)k_R + \frac{(1 - \varepsilon_P)k_P(1 + \varepsilon_N)k_N}{(1 - \varepsilon_R)k_P + (1 + \varepsilon_N)k_N} = 0 \quad (41.a)$$

$$\Rightarrow k_P = -\frac{(1 - \varepsilon_R)(1 + \varepsilon_N)}{(1 - \varepsilon_P)[(1 - \varepsilon_R) + (1 + \varepsilon_N)(k_N/k_R)]} k_N \quad (41.b)$$

Equations (41) show the dependence of k_P on $k_N, k_R, \varepsilon_N, \varepsilon_P, \varepsilon_R$. The values of $\varepsilon_N, \varepsilon_P, \varepsilon_R$ are fixed parameters and k_N is obtained through the optimization; hence the value of k_P can be derived from the above.

3.4 Selection of objective function

As discussed, the parameters of the proposed SDA shown in Fig 1(c) are optimized in order to reduce the structure's absolute accelerations. The primary objective function under the proposed approach is the quantity Q_{AS} derived through Equation (33.c) and repeated below for convenience

$$Q_{AS} = \int_{\omega_1}^{\omega_2} |\tilde{H}_{AS}(\omega)|^2 d\omega \quad (33.c)$$

where $\tilde{H}_{AS}(\omega)$ is calculated via equations (30), (31), (32). Q_{AS} represents the area under the acceleration transfer function of the system and is a measure of the transmissibility of the system. Hence this quantity is an accurate indicator of the portion of energy that is transferred to the structure as absolute acceleration, and consequently of the magnitude of the expected force reactions borne by the structure during the earthquake. It is noted that this method does not require the use of a specific excitation power spectrum or time history excitation, leading to an optimized design that depends solely on the characteristics of the structure that can be used across a range of low-frequency excitations.

As a secondary approach, and for the purposes of comparison and verification of the proposed method, the quantity R_{AS} as defined in equation (35-c) is used as an alternative objective function:

$$R_{AS} = \sqrt{\int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} S_{AS}(\omega) d\omega} \quad (35.c)$$

R_{AS} is an indicator of the energy content of the response to a *specific* excitation PSD that has been previously used in the literature [38]. However, results are expected to present some differences as the stiff dynamic vibration absorber proposed in this work is designed with different static (high) and dynamic (low) stiffnesses.

The extent to which the response results derived from solving the problem with either one of the two objective functions are equivalent is explored in section 4.2.

4 Optimization results and analysis of design factors

4.1 Optimization results for reference design problem

The optimal parameters for the reference SDA design are calculated according to the optimization procedure described in section 3, using the interior-point optimization method. Tables 1 and 2 below show the full set of parameters for the design of the optimized SDA:

Objective function	$X_{I/SD}$ (cm)	m_S (kg)	m_D (kg)	k_R (kN/m)	ε_N (%)	ε_P (%)	ε_R (%)
Q_{AS}	2	1000	50	490.50	10.00	5.00	5.00

Table 1: Fixed parameters & objective function for the optimized SDA

k_N (kN/m)	μ_b (%)	k_P (kN/m)	ζ_N (%)	c_N (kNs/m)	ζ_P (%)	c_P (kNs/m)
-86.45	43	125.76	1.00	0.442	1.00	0.442

Table 2: Optimized parameters & dependent variables for the optimized SDA

The fundamental eigenfrequency for the optimized system is derived from equation (32) for the above parameters equal to 1.87Hz.

The next paragraphs present a comparison of the dynamic responses of the optimized SDA vs. a highly damped ($\zeta=15\%$) conventional damper (CD). Also, the impact of the following design factors to the optimization problem are investigated:

- effect of objective function;
- effect of inerter between the structure and base;
- effect of additional internal inerters;
- alternative vertical static stiffness k_S

For the evaluation of the above, the database of 50 artificial accelerograms generated to match the EC8 spectrum with characteristics “Type 1 with spectral acceleration $a_{vg}=0.9*0.36$ (g)” [38] will be used.

4.2 Effect of objective function

As discussed in section 3.1, one of the motivations of this paper is to explore the equivalence of using Q_{AS} as the objective function for the SDA optimization vs. using R_{AS} , the latter being the approach used in the optimization of the stiff vertical dynamic absorber [38]. Q_{AS} refers to the area under the acceleration transfer function of the system, whereas R_{AS} utilizes the specific acceleration PSD discussed in Appendix C for the optimization of the system parameters. Table 3 below shows the optimized and dependent parameters derived under each method, while the fixed parameters remain the same as the ones shown in Table 1:

Objective function	μ_b (%)	k_N (kN/m)	k_P (kN/m)	ζ_N (%)	c_N (kNs/m)	ζ_P (%)	c_P (kNs/m)
Q_{AS}	43	-86.45	125.76	1.00	0.442	1.00	0.442
R_{AS}	50	-89.21	130.86	1.00	0.442	1.00	0.442

Table 3: Main parameters of the system optimized with the two different objective functions

Below are the results showing the peak values across the sample of the 50 artificial accelerograms for the main quantities of interest (structure absolute acceleration a_s and structure relative displacement u_s) for the optimized SDA under each method, compared to the conventional damper. It can be verified that the two objective functions yield remarkably similar results across all quantities of interest. **This important observation implies that it is possible to use a single optimal SDA design across a range of potential excitations, as the optimization depends solely on the characteristics of the structure.** Furthermore, exploiting the dynamics of the problem and more specifically the properties of the pertinent transfer functions (Appendix B, eq. B-16), the SDA design approach can be implemented regardless of the point of the exciting vertical force (ground or structure). Moreover, it is observed that the proposed optimized system can reduce the structure peak acceleration up to more than 50% when compared to a conventional damping system, while maintaining the displacement within a satisfactory range.

Fig 3 Results from the time history responses of 50 artificial accelerograms with the SDA optimized with the two different objective functions, Q_{AS} and R_{AS} , and for the conventional damper (CD). (a) Peak absolute acceleration averaged over the 50 accelerograms; (b) overall maximum of peak absolute acceleration; (c) overall maximum of peak relative structure displacement

4.3 Effect of inerter between the structure and the base

The proposed SDA includes an inerter between the structure and the base, as shown in Fig1(c). The equivalent mass μ_b is one of the four optimized parameters. The inerter is expected to assist in the reduction of the natural frequency of the system, without the need of additional heavy masses. In order to evaluate the effect of the inerter,

results are calculated for an SDA configuration where the inerter mass is set to zero (SDA-No Inerter) and compared to the proposed SDA. The optimized and dependent parameters for the two cases can be seen in the Table 4 below.

	μ_b (%)	k_N (kN/m)	k_R (kN/m)	k_P (kN/m)	ζ_N (%)	c_N (kNs/m)	ζ_P (%)	c_P (kNs/m)
SDA	43	-86.45	490.50	125.76	1.00	0.442	1.00	0.442
SDA-NI	0	-103.63	490.50	158.85	1.00	0.442	1.00	0.442

Table 4: Main parameters of the system optimized with an inerter (SDA) and without an inerter (SDA-NI)

Figure 4 shows the results corresponding to the time history responses of the 50 artificial accelerograms for the SDA, the SDA-NI (No Inerter) and the conventional damping system. It is confirmed that the SDA design that includes the inerter leads to significantly decreased structure peak absolute accelerations and relative displacements.

Fig 4 Results from the time history responses of 50 artificial accelerograms comparing the optimized SDA (including an inerter between the structure-base), the optimized SDA-NI (not including an inerter) and the conventional damper (CD). (a) Peak absolute acceleration averaged over the 50 accelerograms; (b) overall maximum of peak absolute acceleration; (c) overall maximum of peak relative structure displacement

4.4 Effect of additional internal inerters

An alternative design of the SDA includes the addition of two additional inerters, b_N , b_P placed in parallel to the spring elements k_N , k_P as shown in Fig1(d), forming SDA-II (Internal Inerters). The equivalent masses of the additional inerters are set to 5% of the mass of the structure. The optimization and response of the system is calculated similarly to the SDA, based on the transfer function derived in paragraph 2.4. The basic system parameters are summarized in the table below:

	μ_N (%)	μ_P (%)	μ_b (%)	k_N (kN/m)	k_R (kN/m)	k_P (kN/m)	ζ_N (%)	ζ_P (%)
SDA	0.0	0.0	43.1	-219.80	490.50	529.00	5.0	5.0
SDA-II	5.0	5.0	27.5	-224.44	490.50	552.73	5.0	5.0

Table 5: Main parameters of the system optimized with one inerter between the structure -base (SDA) and with two additional internal inerters in parallel to the k_P , k_N spring elements (SDA-II)

Fig 5 shows the peak structure acceleration, structure peak relative displacement and oscillating mass peak relative displacement over the 50 artificial accelerograms. The oscillating mass relative displacement is additionally presented hereby in order to investigate whether the supplementary internal forces would have any significant effect on it.

Results suggest that no substantial improvement in the response of the SDA-II vs. the proposed SDA design is achieved by the additional inerters.

4.5 Effect of alternative static stiffness

The static stiffness is a fixed design parameter driving the static vertical displacement X_{VSD} (eq. (24)). Table 6 below shows the key parameters of the system optimized for different values of X_{VSD} . The response results across the 50 artificial accelerograms are summarized in Figure 6. The system exhibits a good behavior in the entire range of X_{VSD} , with the SDA resulting to 40%-50% decreased structure acceleration vs. the conventional damper. As expected, a low static stiffness (high X_{VSD}) leads to better isolation (lower structure acceleration) but larger structure relative displacements. The more rigid the initial structure (high static stiffness, low X_{VSD}) the more it benefits from the SDA in terms of reduced response accelerations.

Fig 5 Results from the time history responses of 50 artificial accelerograms comparing the optimized SDA (with a single inerter between the structure-base), the optimized SDA-II (with two additional internal inerters in parallel to the k_P , k_N), and for the conventional damper (CD). (a) Overall maximum of peak absolute acceleration; (b) overall maximum of peak relative structure displacement; (c) overall maximum of oscillating mass peak relative displacement

	μ_b (%)	k_N (kN/m)	k_R (kN/m)	k_P (kN/m)	ζ_N (%)	c_N (kNs/m)	ζ_P (%)	c_P (kNs/m)
$X_{VSD}=1\text{cm}$	59.7	-164.31	981.00	236.03	1.00	0.626	1.00	0.626
$X_{VSD}=2\text{cm}$	43.1	-86.45	490.50	125.76	1.00	0.442	1.00	0.442
$X_{VSD}=3\text{cm}$	35.8	-59.10	327.00	86.55	1.00	0.362	1.00	0.362

Table 6: Main parameters of the system optimized for different values of X_{VSD} in the range [1 3] (cm)

Fig 6 Results from the time history responses of 50 artificial accelerograms with the SDA optimized for varying values of the static deflection X_{VSD} in the range [1 3] (cm). (a) Peak absolute acceleration averaged over the 50 accelerograms; (b) overall maximum of peak absolute acceleration; (c) overall maximum of peak relative structure displacement

5 Validation of the Stiff Dynamic Absorber performance with real earthquake records

The analysis of the various design factors in paragraphs 4.2-4.5 based on the database of 50 artificial accelerograms confirms that the optimal SDA design for a rigid mass of 1000kg corresponds to the configuration of Fig 1(c) with the parameters shown in Tables 1 and 2. The efficiency of this SDA system is subsequently tested for real vertical earthquake motions from the PEER Ground Motion Database. Table 7 shows the selected earthquakes along with their respective information. In this study, earthquakes with an epicentral distance R_{jb} of fewer than 15km, were classified as near-fault earthquake records.

	Earthquake	Date	Recording station	M_w	PGA (g)	R_{jb} (km)	dt (sec)	Dur. ⁵⁻⁹⁵ (sec)
1	Bam	2003	Bam	6.6	0.97	0.05	0.005	9.6
2	Cape Mendocino	1992	Petrolia	7.01	0.15	35.1	0.02	17.7
3	Cape Mendocino	4/25/1992	Cape Mendocino	7.01	0.74	0.0	0.02	9.7
4	Chi-Chi	1999	TCU045	7.62	0.356	26.0	0.005	11.3
5	Chi-Chi	9/20/1999	CHY028	7.62	0.34	3.12	0.005	8.7
6	Corinth	1981	Corinth	6.6	0.1111	10.27	0.01	15.4
7	Ierissos	1983	Ierissos	6.7	0.0088	65.67	0.0024	9.4
8	Imperial Valley	10/15/1979	El Centro Array #4	6.53	0.29	4.9	0.005	10.3
9	Kalamata	1986	Kalamata	6.2	0.2207	6.45	0.0024	6.1
10	Griva	1990	Kilkis	6.1	0.03	26.75	0.01	11.6
11	Kobe	1/16/1995	Kobe University	6.9	0.45	0.9	0.01	7.0
12	Kocaeli	1999	Fatih	7.51	0.133	53.34	0.005	34.3
13	Kocaeli	1999	Izmit	7.51	0.145	3.62	0.005	15.1
14	Kozani	1995	Kastoria	6.4	0.017	47.79	0.005	15.8

	Earthquake	Date	Recording station	M_w	PGA (g)	R_{jb} (km)	dt (sec)	Dur. ₅₋₉₅ (sec)
15	Kozani	1995	Kozani	6.4	0.073	14.13	0.005	8.6
16	Landers	1992	Coolwater	7.28	0.17	19.74	0.0039	10.6
17	Landers	6/28/1992	Lucerne	7.28	0.82	2.19	0.005	13.8
18	L'Aquila	4/6/2009	L'Aquila - Parking	6.3	0.37	0.0	0.005	11.6
19	Loma Prieta	10/18/1989	BRAN	6.93	0.51	3.85	0.005	9.8
20	Northridge	1994	Moorpark	6.69	0.14	26.4	0.02	16.1
21	Northridge	1994	Rinaldi	6.7	0.852	7.1	0.01	9.1
22	Northridge	1978	Tarzana	6.69	1	0.37	0.02	12.6
23	Northridge	1/17/1994	Simi Valley – Katherine Rd	6.69	0.40	0.0	0.01	6.7
24	San Fernando	1971	Castaic	6.61	0.167	19.33	0.01	16.8
25	Tabas	1978	Tabas	7.35	0.641	1.79	0.02	16.5

Table 7. Real earthquake records used for the validation of the SDA efficiency

5.1 General observations

The design analysis discussed in paragraphs 4.2-4.5 has also been applied to the individual real earthquake records and the results are presented in Appendix D. The time history results are in agreement with the observations made for the artificial accelerograms regarding the impact that the objective function, the inerters and the static stiffness have on the optimal SDA design.

Fig 7 below shows the *Peak as-to-PGA* percentage ratio for the 25 real earthquakes listed in Table 7, for the optimized SDA compared to the conventional damper. It is important to observe that the optimized SDA system is capable of reducing structure acceleration for all records (all blue bars are below 100%). The efficiency of the SDA is pronounced in cases of substantial content in the lower frequency range, where the conventional damper would be insufficient as it could amplify structure accelerations.

As mentioned, the records can be categorized according to their distance from epicenter as near-fault (distance <15km) and far-fault (distance >15km). The average *Peak as-to-PGA* ratio for the near-fault records is 47% using the SDA vs. 99% using the conventional damper. The average *Peak as-to-PGA* ratio for the far-fault records is calculated 64% for the SDA vs. 142% for the conventional damper.

Fig 7 Ratios of the peak absolute structure acceleration response *Peak as-to-PGA* for the 25 real earthquakes. Comparison of the time responses of the optimized SDA (blue) vs. the conventional damper CD (red). X-axis index corresponding to earthquake# of Table 7.

In order to validate the efficiency of the proposed SDA on relative structure displacement (u_s), the ten earthquakes that resulted to highest peak u_s have been selected and compared to the corresponding result in case of a conventional damping system. It can be confirmed that even in the cases where the SDA results to larger structure displacement

than the conventional damper, the absolute magnitude remains within reasonable levels (below 2.5 cm). Moreover, the SDA is shown to significantly decrease peak u_S in the case of Northridge Tarzana, where the conventional damper would amplify ground motion (see Figure 7, earthquake #22).

Fig 8 Maximum structure displacement u_S calculated for the proposed SDA (blue) vs. u_S for the conventional damping system CD (red)

5.2 Analysis of selected time histories

A number of real earthquake records are selected in order to analyze the performance of the optimized SDA vs. the conventional damping system. For each record, the time histories of structure acceleration and relative displacement are shown, followed by each earthquake's PSD. The records were chosen so as to cover highest/lowest positive impact of the SDA vs. the conventional damper (based on Figures 7 and 8) and different frequency and acceleration profiles. Figure 9 shows the earthquake with the highest PGA, Northridge Tarzana (#2 from Table 7), and the earthquakes where the SDA system showed the maximum and minimum improvement in terms of a_s -to- PGA , when compared to a conventional damping system, i.e. Loma Prieta and Kobe respectively (#19 and #11 from Fig 7).

As indicated in Fig 7 and 9(a),(b), in both cases of Northridge Tarzana (#22) and Loma Prieta (#19) the SDA achieves an at least 40% decrease of the PGA, whereas the conventional damping system increases the PGA by more than 30%. This can be justified by the frequency content of the two records. Based on the PSDs from Fig 9(g) and (h), both earthquakes have substantial frequency content in the range 3-5Hz, which is close to the natural frequency of ~ 3.5 Hz of the conventional system; hence not only does the conventional isolation system not improve the dynamic performance but in fact it results to higher values of peak structure acceleration and peak relative displacement. Conversely, the SDA decreases the fundamental frequency of the system below 2Hz, hence allowing for a dramatically improved dynamic behavior.

On the other hand, the Kobe record contains some exceptionally low frequency content, in the range of ~ 0 -2Hz (Fig 9(i)) which is mostly below the fundamental frequency of the SDA. It is hence expected that the SDA and the conventional damper exhibit similar dynamic behavior in terms of structure acceleration, achieving isolation only for frequency content higher than 5Hz that is present in the Kobe example (#11 from Fig 7).

Fig 9 Time histories and PSDs of real earthquake records: Northridge (Tarzana st., #22), Loma Prieta (#19) and Kobe (#11). (a), (b), (c): Structure acceleration vs. time for the optimized SDA and the conventional damper (CD); (d), (e), (f): Structure relative displacement vs. time for the optimized SDA and the conventional damper (CD); (g), (h), (i): Frequency PSDs

Figure 10 presents another selection of records with variable frequency content leading to different effects of the SDA. Landers (Lucerne station #17) has its major frequency components around $\sim 12-15$ Hz (Fig 10(g)). As a consequence, the SDA has a dynamic performance similar to the conventionally damped system (Fig 10(a)). Another important observation is the fact that in this specific example, the use of Q_{AS} as the objective function vs. R_{AS} (see discussion in paragraph 4.2) has led to a notably improved dynamic performance of the SDA. As shown in Appendix D, Table D-1 the case of Landers Lucerne (#17) has the highest difference between the Q_{AS} and R_{AS} optimization (11%). This can be explained by the fact that the PSD utilized for the R_{AS} optimization has a frequency concentration at 5-7 Hz; thus, the optimization via Q_{AS} , which does not depend on a specific PSD, yields better results. The opposite is true for the case of Northridge Tarzana (#22), where its PSD concentration at 5Hz results to a 5% improved peak acceleration for the optimization via R_{AS} compared to Q_{AS} (Appendix D, Table D-1).

Figure 10(b) shows the record of Kozani (#14), as the case of the lowest SDA performance in terms of achieved isolation, but dramatically better than the CD (Fig 7: a_s -to-PGA of 95% for the SDA vs. 167% for the CD). The PSD is concentrated at $\sim 1-4$ Hz and the SDA has achieved an excellent isolation vs. the CD for frequencies $\sim 3-4$ Hz (Fig 10(b)). Finally, the case of Cape Mendocino (#3) is also one of the few examples that the SDA does not significantly decrease the acceleration response, due to the fact that the PSD has a peak at exceptionally low frequencies $\sim 0.5-1.5$ Hz, and is otherwise widely distributed in the range $\sim 2-18$ Hz (Fig 10(i)). This last feature contributes to resonance-type effects for the two eigenfrequencies of the SDA, hence allowing for a relatively high structure displacement of the SDA vs. the CD, but still within the acceptable range of $\sim 0-2.5$ cm (Fig 8 and Fig 10(f)).

Fig 10 Time histories and PSDs of real earthquake records: Landers (Lucerne st., #17), Kozani (Kastoria st. #14) and Cape Mendocino (Cape Mendocino st. #3). (a), (b), (c): Structure acceleration vs. time for the optimized SDA and the conventional damper (CD); (d), (e), (f): Structure relative displacement vs. time for the optimized SDA and the conventional damper (CD); (g), (h), (i): Frequency PSDs

In summary, the time history analysis of a sample of 25 real earthquakes verifies that the optimized SDA achieves at least 40% improved behavior vs. the conventional system for 80% of the cases. The SDA is extremely successful reducing structure acceleration in the low-frequency range of ~2-5Hz, where the conventional system would be insufficient. The very few cases where this SDA effect is less pronounced is attributed to specific cases of peaks at exceptionally low frequencies (examples of #3 and #11), or concentration of higher frequency components that are already reduced by the conventional damping system (example of #17).

6 Conclusions

This paper proposes a stiff dynamic absorber (SDA) combining a negative stiffness element, a tuned-mass damper and an inerter, designed for the protection of structures against low-frequency vertical seismic components. The proposed configuration aims at achieving a reduction of the system's fundamental frequency without the need for additional masses and without decreasing the static stiffness.

The system is configured under a proper optimization procedure in accordance with standard design practices, which in this particular work is enhanced by the examination of the most appropriate objective function. Furthermore, a detailed evaluation of alternative designs is conducted resulting from time history responses of a reference structure to a database of artificial accelerograms matching the EC8 spectrum. The efficiency of the stiff dynamic absorber is

subsequently tested on a set of 25 real earthquake records, comparing the dynamic behavior of the proposed system to that of a conventional damper, including a case-by-case analysis of individual records.

Based on the results presented herein, the following conclusions are drawn:

- (i) The SDA achieves a great reduction in peak structure acceleration vs. the conventional damping system, while maintaining the structure relative displacement at reasonable levels. More specifically, the proposed configuration reduced the peak structure accelerations more than 40% vs. the conventional system in 80% of the real earthquake record cases, with an excellent performance in the low-frequency range of (~2-5Hz).
- (ii) For the first time in literature, the SDA is designed with a low dynamic stiffness while maintaining its initial high static stiffness, a feature facilitated by its initial static equilibrium position. The results indicate that the optimized SDA can greatly improve the dynamic behavior of the system without inducing large static deflections, which would compromise the structure's weight bearing capacity.
- (iii) The SDA is optimized via a newly introduced objective function that depends only on the characteristics of the system and not a specific excitation PSD. The response results were compared to those derived from previous practices that used a specific excitation PSD in the objective function, yielding practically similar, or in many cases better, results. Hence, the introduced approach allows for the use of a unique optimal SDA design regardless of the excitation. Furthermore, due to the dynamics of the problems, this design approach can be extended to a wide range of vertical dynamic absorption application such as machine or impact noise insulation.

The SDA configuration is realistic, as it takes into account variations in all stiffness elements and employs a small additional mass (5%). This work includes an indicative implementation of the various design elements demonstrating the feasibility of the proposed configuration.

Appendix A. Analysis of the proposed indicative implementation of the assembly

The potential energy of the assembly in Figure 2 is:

$$U_H = \frac{1}{2} 2k_H (l_{HI} - l_H)^2 \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where k_H is the stiffness of the inclined spring, l_H its length at position u and l_{HI} its initial (uncompressed) length. The spring compression is denoted by $v(u)$:

$$v(u) = l_{HI} - l_H \quad (\text{A.2})$$

Equation (A-1) becomes:

$$U_H = \frac{1}{2} 2k_H v^2 \quad (\text{A.3})$$

The negative stiffness force of the assembly results as

$$N = \frac{\partial U_H}{\partial u} = 2k_H v \frac{\partial v}{\partial u} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

and the negative stiffness k_N is:

$$k_N = \frac{\partial N}{\partial u} = 2k_H \left[\left(\frac{\partial v}{\partial u} \right)^2 + v \left(\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial u^2} \right) \right] \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Moreover, the compression force Q on the spring k_H is:

$$Q(u) = 2k_H v \quad (\text{A.6})$$

In view of Fig 2 the following equations hold:

$$l_H = b - w \quad (\text{A.7.a})$$

$$w = [a^2 - u^2]^{1/2} \quad (\text{A.7.b})$$

The combination of eq. (A-2) and (A-7) leads to:

$$\frac{\partial v}{\partial u} = -\frac{\partial l_H}{\partial u} = \frac{\partial w}{\partial u} = -\frac{u}{w} \quad (\text{A.8})$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 v}{\partial u^2} = \frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial u^2} = -\frac{a^2}{w^3} \quad (\text{A.9})$$

As a result, equations (A-4) and (A-5) become:

$$N(u) = 2k_H(l_{H1} - l_H)\left(-\frac{u}{w}\right) = -2k_H\left[1 - \frac{b - l_{H1}}{a} \frac{a}{w}\right]u \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$k_N(u) = 2k_H\left[\left(\frac{u}{w}\right)^2 - (l_{H1} - l_H)\left(-\frac{a^2}{w^3}\right)\right] = 2k_H\left[1 - \frac{b - l_{H1}}{a} \left(\frac{a}{w}\right)^3\right]u \quad (\text{A.11})$$

Introducing the notations

$$c_l = \frac{b - l_{H1}}{a} \quad (\text{A.12.a})$$

$$c = w/a = [1 - (u/a)^2]^{1/2} \quad (\text{A.12.b})$$

equations (A-11) and (A-12) become:

$$N(u) = -2k_H[1 - c_l/c]u \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$k_N(u) = -2k_H[1 - c_l/c^3] \quad (\text{A.14})$$

Appendix B. SDA under external force excitation

Considering an external force $f(t) = \tilde{F}e^{j\omega t}$ acting on the structure of Fig 1.c (while $X_G=0$), the equations of motions of the two masses take the form:

$$(m_S + b_R)\ddot{x}_S + c_P(\dot{x}_S - \dot{x}_D) + k_R x_S + k_P(x_S - x_D) = \tilde{F}e^{j\omega t} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

$$m_D\ddot{x}_D + c_P(\dot{x}_D - \dot{x}_S) + c_N\dot{x}_D + k_N x_D + k_P(x_D - x_S) = 0 \quad (\text{B.2})$$

The steady state responses of the system are

$$x(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{X}_S \\ \tilde{X}_D \end{bmatrix} e^{j\omega t} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

where \tilde{X}_S, \tilde{X}_D , denote the response complex amplitudes. The above-mentioned equations of motion of the system hence become:

$$-\omega^2(m_S + b_R)\tilde{X}_S + j\omega c_P(\tilde{X}_S - \tilde{X}_D) + k_R\tilde{X}_S + k_P(\tilde{X}_S - \tilde{X}_D) = \tilde{F} \quad (\text{B.4})$$

$$-\omega^2 m_D \tilde{X}_D + j\omega c_p (\tilde{X}_D - \tilde{X}_S) + j\omega c_N \tilde{X}_D + k_N \tilde{X}_D + k_p (\tilde{X}_D - \tilde{X}_S) = 0 \quad (\text{B.5})$$

The complex amplitude \tilde{F} of the acting force can be conveniently written in terms of the complex amplitude of the displacement \tilde{X}_{ST} and total stiffness k_T :

$$\tilde{F}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} k_T \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \tilde{X}_{ST} \quad (\text{B.6})$$

The resulting transfer functions (TFs) of the displacement are

$$\begin{bmatrix} \tilde{H}_{XS} \\ \tilde{H}_{XD} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \tilde{X}_S / X_{ST} \\ \tilde{X}_D / X_{ST} \end{bmatrix} = H^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} k_T \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.7})$$

where \tilde{H} has been defined in (31) as

$$\tilde{H} = \begin{bmatrix} -\omega^2 (m_S + b_R) + j\omega c_p + (k_R + k_p) & -(j\omega c_p + k_p) \\ -(j\omega c_p + k_p) & -\omega^2 m_D + j\omega (c_p + c_N) + (k_N + k_p) \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.8})$$

The resulting force f_B at the base is calculated as:

$$f_B = f(t) - m_S \ddot{X}_S - m_D \ddot{X}_D \quad (\text{B.9})$$

Hence the TF of the force at the base is:

$$\tilde{H}_{FB} = \frac{\tilde{F}_B}{\tilde{F}} = \frac{\tilde{F} + \omega^2 m_S \tilde{X}_S + \omega^2 m_D \tilde{X}_D}{\tilde{F}} \quad (\text{B.10})$$

In view of (B-6) the above reads

$$\tilde{H}_{FB} = 1 + \frac{\omega^2}{k_T} (m_S \tilde{H}_{XS} + m_D \tilde{H}_{XD}) \quad (\text{B.11})$$

where

$$\tilde{H}_{XS} = \frac{k_T \tilde{H}_{22}}{D} \quad (\text{B.12.a})$$

$$\tilde{H}_{XD} = \frac{k_T \tilde{H}_{12}}{D} \quad (\text{B.12.b})$$

and $D = \tilde{H}_{11} \tilde{H}_{22} - \tilde{H}_{12}^2$ is the determinant of the matrix \tilde{H} . It follows that:

$$\tilde{H}_{FB} = 1 + \omega^2 \frac{m_S \tilde{H}_{22} + m_D \tilde{H}_{12}}{D} = \frac{\tilde{H}_{22}(\tilde{H}_{11} + \omega^2 m_S) - \tilde{H}_{12}(\tilde{H}_{12} + \omega^2 m_D)}{D} \quad (\text{B.13})$$

Turning to paragraph 2.3 and in view of equation (31.a), the transfer function of the structure acceleration a_s for a ground acceleration excitation of amplitude A_G is calculated:

$$\tilde{H}_{AS} = 1 - \omega^2 \tilde{H}_{US} = 1 - \frac{\omega^2}{D} (m_S \tilde{H}_{22} + m_D \tilde{H}_{12}) \quad (\text{B.14})$$

Rearranging the above

$$\tilde{H}_{AS} = \frac{\tilde{H}_{22}(\tilde{H}_{11} + \omega^2 m_S) - \tilde{H}_{12}(\tilde{H}_{12} + \omega^2 m_D)}{D} \quad (\text{B.15})$$

In view of the above and (B-13) it follows that:

$$\tilde{H}_{FB} = \tilde{H}_{AS} \quad (\text{B.16})$$

The transfer function of the response structure acceleration for a base excitation is the same as the transfer function of the response force at the base in the case of a force excitation.

Appendix C. Selection of ground motion acceleration excitation power spectrum

Expressions (34) and (35) call for a specific ground excitation profile. The relevant excitation power spectrum is selected following the same procedure used in [38]. The vertical component of the ground motion is described in EN1998-1 [44] by an elastic ground acceleration response spectrum. For each seismic zone the vertical acceleration is given by the ratio av/ag , the recommended values of which are 0.9 for seismic action Type 1 (magnitude $M_w > 5.5$) and 0.45 for Type 2. The basic shape of the spectrum is similar to the recommended horizontal. However, the spectral amplification in the vertical case is 3.0 instead of 2.5. The vertical acceleration response spectrum with spectral acceleration $ag=0.36$ g and Type 1 is can be found in Figure 1(b) of [38].

Fig C-1 Power Spectral Density (PSD) of one of the 50 artificial accelerograms (green), mean PSD of the 50 artificial accelerograms, S_{AM} , (red) and Least Square Fitting (LSF), S_A , of the mean PSD (blue) (Figure 3 of [38]).

A database of 50 artificial accelerograms was generated matching the aforementioned spectrum using the SeismoArtif Software [45]. The method used for the generation of each accelerogram was the “Artificial Accelerogram Generation & Adjustment”, an iterative procedure based on the adaptation of a random process [46] to a target spectrum, which in this case is that of EC8 described above. The process can be summarized as follows:

A random process is used for the generation of a large enough set of phase angles for a series of sinusoidal waves, the sum of which comprise a periodic function. To simulate the transient nature of the earthquakes, the steady state motions are multiplied by a relevant envelope shape (or intensity function), forming an initial artificial accelerogram. In each iteration, this is transferred to the frequency domain using the Fourier Transformation Method, and it is corrected to match the target spectrum. Subsequently, the Inverse Fourier Transform is utilized for the appropriate PGA and Baseline corrections in the time domain. The Fourier Transformation Method is again applied on the corrected accelerogram and the same process is repeated until convergence is achieved. An example of such generated accelerogram can be found in Figure 1(c) of [38].

The mean acceleration response spectrum of the 50 artificial accelerograms of the database compared to the EC8 design vertical acceleration response spectrum has been shown in Figure 1.(b) of [38]. An accurate match is observed with a percentage deviation under 10% in all the range of the natural periods.

The mean power spectral density S_{AM} of the 50 accelerograms is calculated (Figure C-1). Finally, the PSD of the ground motion acceleration, S_A , which is used for the calculation of R_{AS} in eq. 35.c is calculated as the least-square fitting curve of the mean power spectral density S_{AM} . S_{AM} together with the PSD of a random artificial accelerogram are also shown in Figure C-1.

Appendix D. Effect of key SDA design factors to real earthquakes records

D.1 Effect of objective function

Table D-1 below presents the results of the SDA optimized with the two different objective functions, Q_{AS} and R_{AS} , defined in equations (33.c) and (35.c) respectively and discussed in paragraph 3.4. Peak response quantities (structure acceleration, a_s , structure relative displacement, u_s , oscillating mass relative displacement, u_D) are shown for the SDA optimized under each method, and for the conventional damping system. The results verify the equivalency of the two methods in terms of the resulting response.

	Earthquake	Peak a_s (m/s ²)				Peak u_s (cm)				Peak u_D (cm)		
		Qas	Ras	Dif. ¹	CD	Qas	Ras	Dif. ¹	CD	Qas	Ras	Dif. ¹
1	Bam	3.5	3.5	0%	6.5	1.4	1.4	-1%	1.3	5.0	4.9	2%
2	Cape Mendocino P.	1.2	1.2	-1%	2.6	0.7	0.8	-2%	0.5	2.7	2.7	1%
3	Cape Mendocino CM.	4.0	4.3	-6%	5.2	2.2	2.2	-2%	1.0	6.8	6.9	-1%
4	Chi-Chi TCU045	2.0	1.9	3%	2.6	1.3	1.3	-4%	0.5	4.7	4.8	-1%
5	Chi-Chi	1.7	1.7	2%	2.9	0.8	0.8	-5%	0.6	2.8	2.8	-1%
6	Corinth CHY028	0.6	0.6	-1%	1.6	0.4	0.4	-5%	0.3	1.3	1.3	-3%
7	Ierissos	0.1	0.1	4%	0.1	0.0	0.0	-4%	0.0	0.1	0.1	1%
8	Imperial Valley	1.1	1.1	2%	1.9	0.6	0.6	-1%	0.4	2.1	2.1	0%
9	Kalamata	1.0	1.0	3%	2.6	0.4	0.4	6%	0.5	1.5	1.5	0%
10	Griva	0.2	0.2	6%	0.4	0.1	0.1	0%	0.1	0.5	0.5	2%
11	Kobe	2.2	2.3	-7%	2.4	1.1	1.1	-3%	0.5	3.4	3.5	-2%
12	Kocaeli Fatih	0.5	0.5	-8%	1.4	0.2	0.2	1%	0.3	0.8	0.8	4%
13	Kocaeli Izmit	0.6	0.6	0%	1.3	0.3	0.3	-4%	0.3	1.2	1.2	-1%
14	Kozani Kastoria	0.1	0.1	2%	0.2	0.1	0.1	-6%	0.0	0.3	0.3	-3%
15	Kozani Kozani	0.3	0.3	-4%	1.0	0.1	0.1	1%	0.2	0.5	0.5	5%
16	Landers Coolwater	1.1	1.1	5%	2.9	0.6	0.6	-3%	0.6	2.3	2.3	1%
17	Landers Lucerne	2.8	3.1	-11%	3.3	1.0	1.0	-4%	0.6	3.5	3.5	-1%
18	L'Aquila	1.6	1.7	-1%	3.2	1.0	1.1	-5%	0.6	3.8	3.8	-2%
19	Loma Prieta	1.7	1.6	5%	6.5	0.7	0.7	-1%	1.3	2.9	2.8	4%
20	Northridge Moorpark	0.8	0.8	1%	2.1	0.4	0.5	-1%	0.4	1.5	1.5	0%
21	Northridge Rinaldi	4.4	4.5	-3%	12.3	2.3	2.4	-4%	2.4	7.8	8.0	-3%

	Earthquake	Peak a_s (m/s ²)				Peak u_s (cm)				Peak u_D (cm)		
		Qas	Ras	Dif. ¹	CD	Qas	Ras	Dif. ¹	CD	Qas	Ras	Dif. ¹
22	Northridge Tarzana	6.0	5.7	5%	18.5	2.3	2.2	5%	3.6	8.3	7.8	7%
23	Northridge SV-Kath.Rd	2.1	2.0	3%	2.8	1.3	1.3	-2%	0.5	4.6	4.6	-1%
24	San Fernando	1.0	0.9	8%	2.5	0.4	0.4	3%	0.5	1.7	1.6	5%
25	Tabas	3.4	3.4	1%	6.1	1.5	1.5	-1%	1.2	5.3	5.3	1%

Table D-1. Comparison of the peak response quantities (structure acceleration, a_s , structure relative displacement, u_s , oscillating mass relative displacement, u_D) of the stiff dynamic absorber optimized with two different objective functions, Q_{AS} , R_{AS} , and corresponding quantities of the conventional damping system (CD) for real earthquakes. ¹Difference (%) refers to the percentage increase of each quantity calculated for of the SDA optimized using Q_{AS} as the objective function, vs. using R_{AS} .

D.2 Effect of inerter between structure-base

Table D-2 below presents the results of the system optimized (i) including the inerter b_R placed between the structure and the base (SDA as shown in Fig 1.c), and (ii) without the inerter b_R (SDA-NI). Peak response quantities (structure acceleration, a_s , structure relative displacement, u_s , oscillating mass relative displacement, u_D) are shown for the SDA optimized under each method, and for the conventional damping system. The results verify the beneficial impact of the inerter for all response quantities in almost all the earthquake cases.

	Earthquake	Peak a_s (m/s ²)				Peak u_s (cm)				Peak u_D (cm)		
		SDA	SDA-NI	Dif. ²	CD	SDA	SDA-NI	Dif. ²	CD	SDA	SDA-NI	Dif. ²
1	Bam	3.5	4.0	13%	6.5	1.4	1.7	26%	1.3	5.0	5.2	4%
2	Cape Mendocino P.	1.2	1.7	45%	2.6	0.7	1.0	31%	0.5	2.7	3.2	20%
3	Cape Mendocino CP.	4.0	6.0	47%	5.2	2.2	2.5	16%	1.0	6.8	6.9	0%
4	Chi-Chi TCU045	2.0	2.4	20%	2.6	1.3	1.6	20%	0.5	4.7	5.0	6%
5	Chi-Chi	1.7	1.7	-1%	2.9	0.8	0.9	10%	0.6	2.8	2.9	4%
6	Corinth CHY028	0.6	0.9	58%	1.6	0.4	0.4	8%	0.3	1.3	1.3	-1%
7	Ierissos	0.1	0.1	38%	0.1	0.0	0.0	26%	0.0	0.1	0.1	13%
8	Imperial Valley	1.1	1.4	26%	1.9	0.6	0.7	26%	0.4	2.1	2.3	12%
9	Kalamata	1.0	1.6	64%	2.6	0.4	0.6	39%	0.5	1.5	2.1	39%
10	Griava	0.2	0.3	54%	0.4	0.1	0.2	30%	0.1	0.5	0.6	17%
11	Kobe	2.2	2.8	29%	2.4	1.1	1.2	9%	0.5	3.4	3.5	2%
12	Kocaeli Fatih	0.5	0.6	40%	1.4	0.2	0.3	28%	0.3	0.8	0.9	14%
13	Kocaeli Izmit	0.6	0.8	40%	1.3	0.3	0.4	21%	0.3	1.2	1.2	5%
14	Kozani Kastoria	0.1	0.1	20%	0.2	0.1	0.1	21%	0.0	0.3	0.3	4%
15	Kozani Kozani	0.3	0.4	23%	1.0	0.1	0.2	41%	0.2	0.5	0.6	22%
16	Landers Coolwater	1.1	1.4	21%	2.9	0.6	0.7	18%	0.6	2.3	2.3	1%
17	Landers Lucerne	2.8	2.8	1%	3.3	1.0	1.1	11%	0.6	3.5	3.3	-6%
18	L'Aquila	1.6	2.1	30%	3.2	1.0	1.3	20%	0.6	3.8	3.9	4%
19	Loma Prieta	1.7	2.6	55%	6.5	0.7	1.0	30%	1.3	2.9	3.5	21%
20	Northridge Moorpark	0.8	1.2	44%	2.1	0.4	0.5	16%	0.4	1.5	1.6	11%
21	Northridge Rinaldi	4.4	6.5	50%	12.3	2.3	2.5	6%	2.4	7.8	9.4	21%
22	Northridge Tarzana	6.0	6.9	15%	18.5	2.3	3.2	36%	3.6	8.3	10.7	28%
23	Northridge S.V-Kath.Rd	2.1	2.8	34%	2.8	1.3	1.6	24%	0.5	4.6	5.0	9%
24	San Fernando	1.0	1.2	28%	2.5	0.4	0.6	35%	0.5	1.7	2.0	22%
25	Tabas	3.4	4.1	21%	6.1	1.5	1.7	16%	1.2	5.3	5.6	4%

Table D-2. Comparison of the peak response quantities (structure acceleration, a_s , structure relative displacement, u_s , oscillating mass relative displacement, u_D) of the stiff dynamic absorber optimized (i) with an inerter between the

structure and the base (SDA), and (ii) without an inerter (SDA-NI), and corresponding quantities of the conventional damping system (CD) for real earthquakes. ²Difference (%) refers to the percentage increase of each quantity calculated for the SDA optimized with no inerter vs. the optimization including an inerter.

D.3 Effect of additional internal inerters

Table D-3 below presents the results of the system optimized (i) including a single inerter b_R (SDA as shown in Fig 1.c), and (ii) including two additional inerters, b_N, b_P, b_R (SDA-II as shown in Fig 1.d). Peak response quantities (structure acceleration, a_s , structure relative displacement, u_s , oscillating mass relative displacement, u_D) are shown for the SDA optimized under each method, and for the conventional damping system. The results confirm that the additional inerters do not add a significant advantage in the efficiency of the system.

	Earthquake	Peak a_s (m/s ²)				Peak u_s (cm)				Peak u_D (cm)		
		SDA	SDA-II	Dif. ³	CD	SDA	SDA-II	Dif. ³	CD	SDA	SDA-II	Dif. ³
1	Bam	2.8	2.9	-3%	6.5	2.2	2.3	0%	1.3	3.8	3.9	-1%
2	Cape Mendocino P.	1.1	1.1	0%	2.6	0.8	0.8	2%	0.5	1.4	1.4	0%
3	Cape Mendocino CP.	4.5	4.7	-2%	5.2	3.2	3.2	1%	1.0	5.5	5.6	-1%
4	Chi-Chi TCU045	1.8	1.7	1%	2.6	1.6	1.5	1%	0.5	2.7	2.7	0%
5	Chi-Chi	1.5	1.5	1%	2.9	1.2	1.2	1%	0.6	2.0	2.0	0%
6	Corinth CHY028	0.6	0.6	0%	1.6	0.6	0.6	-1%	0.3	1.0	1.1	-1%
7	Ierissos	0.0	0.0	4%	0.1	0.0	0.0	3%	0.0	0.1	0.1	2%
8	Imperial Valley	0.8	0.8	1%	1.9	0.6	0.6	4%	0.4	1.1	1.0	2%
9	Kalamata	0.8	0.9	-7%	2.6	0.5	0.5	2%	0.5	0.8	0.8	0%
10	Griva	0.2	0.2	-1%	0.4	0.1	0.1	1%	0.1	0.3	0.3	0%
11	Kobe	2.1	2.1	0%	2.4	1.5	1.5	1%	0.5	2.5	2.6	0%
12	Kocaeli Fatih	0.4	0.4	1%	1.4	0.3	0.3	2%	0.3	0.5	0.5	0%
13	Kocaeli Izmit	0.5	0.5	1%	1.3	0.4	0.4	1%	0.3	0.7	0.7	0%
14	Kozani Kastoria	0.1	0.1	0%	0.2	0.1	0.1	0%	0.0	0.2	0.2	-1%
15	Kozani Kozani	0.3	0.3	-3%	1.0	0.2	0.1	4%	0.2	0.3	0.3	1%
16	Landers Coolwater	1.0	0.9	3%	2.9	0.8	0.8	2%	0.6	1.4	1.4	1%
17	Landers Lucerne	2.4	2.4	0%	3.3	1.7	1.7	0%	0.6	2.9	2.9	0%
18	L'Aquila	1.7	1.6	1%	3.2	1.5	1.6	1%	0.6	2.6	2.7	-1%
19	Loma Prieta	1.5	1.5	-1%	6.5	1.1	1.1	1%	1.3	1.9	1.9	-1%
20	Northridge Moorpark	0.7	0.8	-2%	2.1	0.6	0.5	2%	0.4	0.9	0.9	0%
21	Northridge Rinaldi	3.8	4.0	-2%	12.3	3.1	3.0	2%	2.4	5.3	5.3	0%
22	Northridge Tarzana	4.4	4.5	-3%	18.5	2.5	2.3	3%	3.6	4.2	4.1	0%
23	Northridge S.V-Kath.Rd	1.6	1.5	2%	2.8	1.3	1.2	5%	0.5	2.2	2.1	3%
24	San Fernando	0.6	0.6	-4%	2.5	0.5	0.4	2%	0.5	0.8	0.8	1%
25	Tabas	2.5	2.4	1%	6.1	1.9	1.9	0%	1.2	3.2	3.2	0%

Table D-3. Comparison of the peak response quantities (structure acceleration, a_s , structure relative displacement, u_s , oscillating mass relative displacement, u_D) of the stiff dynamic absorber optimized (i) with a single inerter between the structure and the base (SDA), and (ii) with two additional inerters placed in parallel to the k_P, k_N spring elements (SDA-II), and corresponding quantities of the conventional damping system (CD) for real earthquakes. ³Difference (%) refers to the percentage increase of each quantity calculated for the SDA optimized with a single inerter between the structure and the base, vs. the SDA optimized with the two additional inerters (SDA-II).

D.4 Effect of static stiffness k_S

Tables D-4 and D-5 below present the results of the SDA system optimized for different values of static displacement ($X_{VSD}=1,2,3$ cm), compared to the conventional damping system (CD) of corresponding static stiffness.). Peak response quantities (structure acceleration, a_s , structure relative displacement, u_s , oscillating mass relative displacement, u_D) are shown for each earthquake. Structure acceleration, a_s , and structure relative displacement, u_s , are shown in comparison to those of the conventional damping system of corresponding static stiffness.

	Earthquake	Peak a_s (m/s ²)					
		$X_{VSD}=1$ cm	CD	$X_{VSD}=2$ cm	CD	$X_{VSD}=3$ cm	CD
1	Bam	3.4	9.0	3.5	6.5	3.2	4.6
2	Cape Mendocino P.	1.7	2.9	1.2	2.6	1.2	2.6
3	Cape Mendocino CP.	4.6	8.3	4.0	5.2	3.9	5.1
4	Chi-Chi TCU045	2.6	3.0	2.0	2.6	1.8	3.0
5	Chi-Chi	1.8	3.2	1.7	2.9	1.6	2.3
6	Corinth CHY028	0.8	1.7	0.6	1.6	0.6	1.3
7	Ierissos	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.0	0.2
8	Imperial Valley	1.2	2.0	1.1	1.9	0.9	1.9
9	Kalamata	1.5	4.0	1.0	2.6	0.7	2.0
10	Griva	0.3	0.3	0.2	0.4	0.2	0.5
11	Kobe	2.4	4.6	2.2	2.4	2.0	2.2
12	Kocaeli Fatih	0.6	1.2	0.5	1.4	0.5	1.5
13	Kocaeli Izmit	1.0	1.8	0.6	1.3	0.6	1.2
14	Kozani Kastoria	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.2
15	Kozani Kozani	0.5	1.3	0.3	1.0	0.3	0.8
16	Landers Coolwater	1.2	2.9	1.1	2.9	1.0	2.4
17	Landers Lucerne	3.2	5.2	2.8	3.3	2.8	3.4
18	L'Aquila	2.4	4.3	1.6	3.2	1.9	3.2
19	Loma Prieta	2.6	6.0	1.7	6.5	1.5	5.5
20	Northridge Moorpark	1.0	3.0	0.8	2.1	0.7	1.5
21	Northridge Rinaldi	5.6	15.9	4.4	12.3	4.0	7.6
22	Northridge Tarzana	7.5	23.0	6.0	18.5	4.9	13.7
23	Northridge S.V-Kath.Rd	2.1	4.0	2.1	2.8	1.6	2.2
24	San Fernando	1.2	3.1	1.0	2.5	0.8	1.7
25	Tabas	3.9	9.7	3.4	6.1	2.8	6.2

Table D-4. Peak structure acceleration, a_s , for the SDA optimized for different values of static displacement ($X_{VSD}=1,2,3$ cm), compared to the conventional damping system (CD) of corresponding static stiffness.

	Earthquake	Peak u_s (cm)						Peak u_D (cm)		
		$X_{VSD}=1$ cm	CD	$X_{VSD}=2$ cm	CD	$X_{VSD}=3$ cm	CD	$X_{VSD}=1$ cm	$X_{VSD}=2$ cm	$X_{VSD}=3$ cm
1	Bam	0.9	0.9	1.4	1.3	2.1	1.4	3.0	5.0	8.0
2	Cape Mendocino P.	0.6	0.3	0.7	0.5	0.8	0.8	2.1	2.7	3.0
3	Cape Mendocino CP.	1.1	0.8	2.2	1.0	3.1	1.5	3.9	6.8	10.1
4	Chi-Chi TCU045	0.7	0.3	1.3	0.5	1.6	0.9	2.6	4.7	5.9
5	Chi-Chi	0.4	0.3	0.8	0.6	1.2	0.7	1.6	2.8	4.0
6	Corinth CHY028	0.2	0.2	0.4	0.3	0.6	0.4	0.9	1.3	2.2
7	Ierissos	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1
8	Imperial Valley	0.3	0.2	0.6	0.4	0.6	0.6	1.3	2.1	2.1
9	Kalamata	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.6	1.3	1.5	1.7

		Peak u_s (cm)						Peak u_D (cm)		
		$X_{VSD}=1\text{cm}$	CD	$X_{VSD}=2\text{cm}$	CD	$X_{VSD}=3\text{cm}$	CD	$X_{VSD}=1\text{cm}$	$X_{VSD}=2\text{cm}$	$X_{VSD}=3\text{cm}$
10	Griva	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.5
11	Kobe	0.5	0.5	1.1	0.5	1.5	0.6	1.6	3.4	5.5
12	Kocaeli Fatih	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.8	0.8	1.1
13	Kocaeli Izmit	0.2	0.2	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.9	1.2	1.6
14	Kozani Kastoria	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.3	0.3
15	Kozani Kozani	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.6
16	Landers Coolwater	0.3	0.3	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.7	1.2	2.3	3.0
17	Landers Lucerne	0.6	0.5	1.0	0.6	1.6	1.0	2.1	3.5	5.4
18	L'Aquila	0.6	0.4	1.0	0.6	1.6	0.9	2.4	3.8	5.8
19	Loma Prieta	0.7	0.6	0.7	1.3	1.1	1.6	2.9	2.9	3.7
20	Northridge Moorpark	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.4	0.6	0.4	1.1	1.5	1.9
21	Northridge Rinaldi	1.5	1.6	2.3	2.4	3.2	2.2	5.7	7.8	10.2
22	Northridge Tarzana	1.9	2.2	2.3	3.6	2.3	3.9	7.9	8.3	7.1
23	Northridge S.V-Kath.Rd	0.6	0.4	1.3	0.5	1.3	0.7	2.3	4.6	5.0
24	San Fernando	0.3	0.3	0.4	0.5	0.5	0.5	1.1	1.7	1.7
25	Tabas	0.9	1.0	1.5	1.2	1.9	1.8	3.4	5.3	6.7

Table D-5. Structure peak relative displacement, u_s and oscillating mass peak relative displacement, u_D , for the SDA optimized for different values of static displacement ($X_{VSD}=1,2,3$ cm). Peak u_s compared to that of the conventional damping system (CD) of corresponding static stiffness.

Appendix E. Indicative implementation of key elements of the SDA configuration: negative stiffness element and inerter

E.1 Detailed design of conventional spring and stress analysis

An indicative example regarding the realization of the NS element having constant NS ($c_f=0$), with the proposed configuration presented in Figure 2 and Appendix A, is presented below. The value (constant) of the NS element is obtained from Table 2 which corresponds to the optimized SDA with an objective function that of Q_{AS} ($k_{NS}=-86.45$ kN/m). The fixed values for this set of optimized parameters are presented in Table 1.

In order for the generated NS to be constant, the dimensionless parameter c_f (Eq. A-12.a) is set equal to zero. Thus, the length of the undeformed conventional stiffness element k_H (l_{HI}) is equal to the parameter b . In addition, in the static equilibrium position, when we consider $c_f=0$, the rod of length a is placed horizontally. As a consequence, the maximum absolute NS element stroke (u_D) is equal to the rod length a .

In Appendix D, the dynamic responses of the SDA are presented for all the considered real earthquake records. It is observed that the maximum (absolute) value of the additional mass relative displacement is below 8 cm, for all real and artificial seismic records. Having this value as an upper limit of the u_D (and thus the NS stroke) the rod length is set equal to 8 cm.

The value of the two horizontal conventional stiffness elements (k_H) is obtained from Eq. A-14 ($k_H=43.225$ kN/m). In this example, the k_H is realized as a conventional spiral spring. The design parameters for this spiral spring are presented in Table E-1, and are selected with analytical expressions [47] in order for the spring to have a factor of safety against torsional yielding at its solid length greater than 1.3, and a factor of safety against buckling greater than 1.2. The material used is chrome-vanadium (ASTM A232 Alloy Steel Wire).

wire diameter d (mm)	Spring mean diameter D (mm)	Number of active coils N_a	Spring index C
11	60	15	5.45
Spring rate	Spring free length	Spring solid length	Maximum deflection

k_H (kN/m)	l_{HI} (mm)	l_s (mm)	
43.61	260 (=b)	176 (< $b-a$)	84 (> $a=UNS$)

Table E-1. Design parameters for the spiral spring that realizes the positive stiffness element k_H .

In addition, a stress analysis for the spiral spring is performed by employing the FE code ABAQUS [48] in order to evaluate the maximum stresses that occur when the spring is fully deformed (8 cm). The mechanical properties used in order to model the spiral spring are obtained from [49]. In Figure E-1, the deflections along the spring length, and the maximum von Mises stresses are presented when the spring with the characteristics presented above, is in its fully deformed state. It is observed that the stresses are retained 25% (safety factor 1.32) below the maximum allowable stress that this material allows.

Fig E-1 (a) Spiral spring deflections along the spring length, and (b) maximum von Mises stresses along the spring length.

E.2 Realization of inerter element

The inerter can be realized by an easy to construct mechanical device proposed in [11], which satisfies certain practical conditions. More specifically, a plunger sliding is inserted in a cylinder which drives a flywheel through a rack, pinion, and gears (see Fig. 3 of [11]). This configuration does not have the limitation that one of the two terminals of the inerter needs to be grounded. To model the dynamics of this device, let r_1 be the radius of the rack pinion, r_2 the radius of the gear wheel, r_3 the radius of the flywheel pinion, γ the radius of gyration of the flywheel, m the mass of the flywheel, and assume the mass of all other components is negligible. The equivalent inertance generated by this mechanical device is:

$$b = \frac{1}{2} m_2 \alpha_1^2 \alpha_2^2 \quad (E.1)$$

where m_2 is the mass of the flywheel, $\alpha_1 = \gamma/r_3$ and $\alpha_2 = r_2/r_1$. The required inertance ratio for the SDA device is $\mu_b = 43\%$, thus for a reference structure mass of 1000 kg, the generated inertance is 430 kg. For $\alpha_1 = \alpha_2 = 5$, and a radius of the flywheel $R_2 = 7.5$ cm with a thickness of 1 cm, the mass of the flywheel (steel) is $m_2 = 1.376$ kg, leading to a generated inertance of 430 kg.

7 Declarations

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7.2 Conflicts of interest/Competing interests

The authors declare there are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

7.3 Availability of data and material

The data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

7.4 Code availability

The data used to support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon request.

7.5 Authors’ contributions

Conceptualization: [M. Kalogerakou, K. Kapasakalis, I. Antoniadis], Methodology: [M. Kalogerakou, K. Kapasakalis, I. Antoniadis], Software: [M. Kalogerakou], Formal analysis: [M. Kalogerakou, I. Antoniadis], Investigation: [M. Kalogerakou], Resources: [M. Kalogerakou, K. Kapasakalis], Data curation: [M. Kalogerakou, K. Kapasakalis], Writing - original draft: [M. Kalogerakou], Visualization: [M. Kalogerakou, K. Kapasakalis, I. Antoniadis], Validation: [M. Kalogerakou], Writing - review & editing: [M. Kalogerakou, K. Kapasakalis, I. Antoniadis], Project administration: [I. Antoniadis, E. Sapountzakis], Funding acquisition: [I. Antoniadis, E. Sapountzakis], Supervision: [I. Antoniadis, E. Sapountzakis].

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